

PERCEPTION OF THE CUSTOMERS TOWARDS E-MARKETING IN ERODE DISTRICT

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Abstract

E-Shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly purchase products or services from seller over the internet using web browser. Growing numbers of consumers shop online to purchase goods and services, gather product information or even browse for enjoyment. E-shopping environments are therefore playing an increasing role in the overall relationship between marketers and their consumers. In this regard, the researcher had aimed to identify the perception level of the consumers towards e-marketing in Erode district of Tamilnadu, India. For this, the researcher has selected 145 respondents in different age groups by using convenient sampling technique. The consumers' opinion towards e-marketing was collected by using structured questionnaire. The collected details were subduced into tables by using percentage analysis, mean score analysis and Anova analysis. From the research, it is found that female, less than 25 years aged, home maker and students have more perception in practicing E-Marketing.

Keywords: e-Shopping, Consumer Perception, e-Marketing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Online shopping is a form of e-commerce which allows consumers to directly purchase products or services from seller over the internet using web browser. Online shopping is a fast growing phenomenon. Growing numbers of consumers shop online to purchase goods and services, gather product information or even browse for enjoyment. Online shopping environments are therefore playing an increasing role in the overall relationship between marketers and their consumers (Koo et al 2008). Due to exponentially rising business opportunities, there are a number of services being offered on the internet. Online shopping has emerged as one of the most prominent services available through internet. It has enormous advantages for the consumers as well as business houses. Through on-line shopping, business houses have been able to reach out to more consumers at less cost. They have been able to reach out to consumers living in remote areas. In-fact these are acting as stepping-stones to concept of global village. More over the inventory management overheads also decrease significantly through online shopping. Consumers can shop from any place and need not physically visit the shops / outlets for shopping purposes. Therefore, even if customer is staying in remote area, he / she can easily shop through internet. However, here consumers can visit any number of sites to reach at final choice. Hence, online shopping provides unlimited choices to the consumers in nut shell. The customer can shop any day of the year on any time of the day. This also

helps in consumers' time and energy saving. More over due to unlimited choice and less excess time, consumers can easily search for the desired things and can easily compare the products / items. Therefore, the present research is made to study the factors affecting online shopping behaviour of consumers in Erode.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Empirical research shows that convenient of the internet is one of the impacts on consumers' willingness to buy online (Wang et al., 2005). Online shopping is available for customers around the clock comparing to traditional store as it is open 24 hours a day, 7 days a week (Hofacker, 2001; Wang et al., 2005). Research shows that 58 percent chose to shop online because they could shop after-hours, when the traditional stores are closed and 61 percent of the respondents selected to shop online because they want to avoid crowds and wailing lines, especially in holiday shopping (The Tech Faq, 2008). Consumers not only look for products, but also for online services. Some companies have online customer services available 24 hours. Therefore, even after business hours, customers can ask questions, get necessary support or assistance, which has provided convenience to consumers (Hermes, 2000).

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

When consumers want to buy product, they will look at the brand and the characteristics of product or service. Some products can be purchased and shipped easily online such as, software, books. On the other hand, some products are hard to decide through online channel. Web site features, firm capabilities, marketing communication stimuli, and consumer skills are also important, in terms of the proposed framework. Web Site feature is one of the important things that can influence consumers to buy product online. For example, online retailers can use high technology to improve their websites in order to influence consumer perceptions of the web environment. If the web site is too slow, not navigability, or not safe enough, will have negatively impact consumer willingness to try or buy products from the website. Among the various back draft of the online purchase behavior of the consumers, the research emerges to examine the customer perception towards E-Marketing in Erode district.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the demographic status with perception level of the customers in Erode.
- To examine the perception level of the customers towards E-Marketing in Erode.

5. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to male and female.
- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different age group of the respondents.

- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different educational qualification of the respondents.
- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different occupation of the respondents.
- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different monthly income level of the respondents.
- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to usage of E-marketing portals of the respondents.
- There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to spending amount of the respondents.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is mainly used descriptive research design. For proofing the above hypotheses, the researcher has used 145 selected respondents who have experience in practicing E-Marketing in Erode district of Tamilnadu, India. A structured questionnaire has framed and collects the opinion of the respondents towards their perception on E-Marketing. The collected information were subdued into tables with the help of statistical tools like percentage analysis, mean score analysis and Anova analysis.

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

The following table shows the demographic condition of the customers towards E-Marketing.

Table 1: Demographic of the Respondents and their Perception

S.No.	Factors	No. of Respondents	%	Mean Score
Gender				
1	Male	113	77.9	3.59
2	Female	32	22.1	3.78
	Total	145	100.0	
Age				
1	Less than 25 years	11	7.6	3.73
2	25 – 35 years	40	27.6	3.65
3	36 – 45 years	66	45.5	3.60
4	Above 45 years	28	19.3	3.64
	Total	145	100.0	
Educational Qualification				
1	No formal education	18	12.4	3.75
2	School level	1	0.7	3.84
3	Graduate	29	20.0	3.84
4	Post Graduate	61	42.1	3.50
5.	Professional	36	24.8	3.62
	Total	145	100.0	

S.No.	Factors	No. of Respondents	%	Mean Score
Occupational Status				
1	Agriculturist	16	11.0	3.59
2	Government Employee	1	0.7	3.58
3	Private Employee	7	4.8	3.64
4	Business	103	71.0	3.62
5	Others (Homemaker, Student, etc.)	18	12.5	3.75
	Total	145	100.0	
Monthly Family Income				
1	Upto Rs.20,000	11	7.6	3.51
2	Rs.20,001 – 40,000	62	42.8	3.59
3	Rs.40,001 – 60,000	61	42.1	3.69
4	Above Rs.60,000	11	7.5	3.67
	Total	145	100.0	
Type of E-Marketing Portals				
1	Amazon	21	14.5	3.47
2	Flipkart	65	44.8	3.76
3	Snap deal	29	20.0	3.60
4	e-Bay	25	17.3	3.50
5	Shopclues	5	3.4	3.47
	Total	145	100.0	
Spending Amount				
1	Less than Rs.2000	24	16.6	3.64
2	Rs.2000 to 4000	70	48.3	3.68
3	Rs.4001 to 6000	20	13.8	3.43
4	Above Rs.6000	31	21.3	3.66
	Total	145	100.0	

From the above analysis, it is observed that majority of the respondents are male, belongs to 36-45 years age group, qualified with post graduate, engaged in their business, earn Rs.20001 to 40,000 as family monthly income, E-Marketing through Flipkart and spent Rs.2000 to 4000 for purchase of products through E-Marketing.

Majority of the respondents have experienced high level of perception in E-Marketing practices who are female, belongs to less than 25 years aged, educated till school and graduate level, status as homemaker, students, etc., around Rs.40001 to 60000 earn monthly in their family, using Flipkart on purchase products and spent around Rs.2000 to 4000 in a month.

7.2 Perception towards E-Marketing

In order to find the relationship between the selected independent variables of the respondents and their perception towards E-Marketing, the following hypothesis has been framed and tested by using Anova test.

H₀₁: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to male and female.

Table 2: Gender and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.878	1	0.878	15.759	0.000**
Within Groups	7.965	143	0.056		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: ** - Significant at 1% level

It is obtained from the above table that the null hypothesis is rejected due to significant result. So, there is a significant difference between the mean perception of male and female customers towards E-Marketing.

H₀₂: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different age group of the respondents.

Table 3: Age and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.177	3	0.059	0.963	0.412 ^{NS}
Within Groups	8.666	141	0.061		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: NS – Not Significant

It is noted from the above table that the null hypothesis is accepted due to not significant result. So, there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different age groups of the respondents towards E-Marketing.

H₀₃: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different educational qualification of the respondents.

Table 4: Educational Qualification and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.584	4	0.646	14.452	0.000**
Within Groups	6.259	140	0.045		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: ** – Significant at 1% level

It is identified from the above table that the null hypothesis is rejected due to significant result. So, there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of different educational qualification of the respondents towards E-Marketing.

H₀₄: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different occupation of the respondents.

Table 5: Occupation and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.313	4	0.078	1.284	0.279 ^{NS}
Within Groups	8.530	140	0.061		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: NS – Not Significant

It is noted from the above table that the null hypothesis is accepted due to not significant result. So, there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different occupational status of the respondents towards E-Marketing.

H₀₅: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to different monthly income level of the respondents.

Table 6: Monthly Income Level and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	0.461	3	0.154	2.587	0.055NS
Within Groups	8.382	141	0.059		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: NS – Not Significant

It is observed from the above table that the null hypothesis is accepted due to not significant result. So, there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different monthly income level of the respondents towards E-Marketing.

H₀₆: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to usage of E-marketing portals of the respondents.

Table 7: Usage of E-marketing Portals and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.235	4	0.559	11.838	0.000**
Within Groups	6.608	140	0.047		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: ** – Significant at 1% level

It is observed from the above table that the null hypothesis is rejected due to significant result. So, there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of usage of E-marketing portals by the respondents towards E-Marketing.

H₀₇: There is no significant mean difference in perception towards E-Marketing with regard to spending amount of the respondents.

Table 8: Spending Amount for Purchase and Perception towards E-Marketing

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.006	3	0.335	6.035	0.001**
Within Groups	7.837	141	0.056		
Total	8.843	144			

Note: ** – Significant at 1% level

It is observed from the above table that the null hypothesis is rejected due to significant result. So, there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of spending amount of the respondents towards purchase through E-marketing.

8. FINDINGS

- From the analysis, it is found that majority of the respondents are male, belongs to 36-45 years age group, qualified with post graduate, engaged in their business, earn Rs.20001 to 40,000 as family monthly income, E-Marketing through Flipkart and spent Rs.2000 to 4000 for purchase of products through E-Marketing.
- It is observed that majority of the respondents have experienced high level of perception in E-Marketing practices who are female, belongs to less than 25 years aged, educated till school and graduate level, status as homemaker, students, etc., around Rs.40001 to 60000 earn monthly in their family, using Flipkart on purchase products and spent around Rs.2000 to 4000 in a month.
- It is found from the analysis that there is a significant difference between the mean perception of male and female customers towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different age groups of the respondents towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of different educational qualification of the respondents towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different occupational status of the respondents towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is no significant difference between the mean perceptions of different monthly income level of the respondents towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of usage of E-marketing portals by the respondents towards E-Marketing.
- It is found from the analysis that there is a significant difference between the mean perceptions of spending amount of the respondents towards purchase through E-marketing.

9. SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

- From the research, male has less perception in E-Marketing than female with less than 25 years aged. It proves the present day buying behavior of the female customers that they have more interested to purchase products through E-Marketing portals than male. It clears the more usage level of E-Marketing portals among female. Also, it indicates more number of female products is available in E-Marketing portals than male. So, the E-Marketing portals may take introduce more attractive products for male customers that may increase the perception level of the male customers.
- Home makers and students have more perception than other category of customers in this study. It indicates more searching time available of the respondents and other side other customers can not able to search and verify their needed products because huge

number of products available in the market. So, the E-Marketing portals may offer unique quality products with unique number may leads to increase the perception level of the customers.

- Most of the respondents attracted the Flipkart E-Marketing portal. So, it is necessary to update the attraction of the other E-Marketing portals with easy searching facilities and comparison of the products. It increases the perception level of the E-Marketing customers.
- Different spending amount of the respondents have different perception towards E-Marketing like their selection of portals and selection of products. So, it has to keenly identify by the E-Marketing portals through different online searching technical tools and offer some attractive discount for the particular customers that may increase the perception level of the E-Marketing customers in the study area.

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